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ABORTION INCONSISTENCY ARGUMENTS: A CATEGORY MISTAKE IN SIMKULET'S DEFENCE

ABSTRACT

Abortion is one of the moral issues that has generated endless debates in the field of ethics. While its opponents (the prolife) reject abortion because a child has a right to live from the moment of conception and that the life should be preserved from that moment, its proponents (the prochoice) accept abortion based on respect for the right of the mother to choose what happens in her body. Among the criticisms against the prolife are abortion inconsistency arguments. In them, the prochoice argue that the prolife are inconsistent by opposing abortion while being silent about other ill conditions of life, like the dying of foetuses through miscarriage and the freezing and destruction of excess IVF embryos. William Simkulet, a proponent of this theory, like others, argues that either the opponents of abortion do more by equally engaging in other issues of life preservation rather than just opposing abortion, or, they should refrain from opposing abortion. Emphatic in his criticism is his view that the opponents of abortion neglect the prevention of miscarriage, which he sees as a point of inconsistency. This paper critiques Simkulet's inconsistency arguments. With an expository and analytical method, the paper argues that Simkulet falls into a category mistake in his treatment of miscarriage as if it belongs to the same category as abortion in moral evaluation. This undermines his inconsistency arguments and makes them implausible.

Keywords: abortion, prolife, prochoice, inconsistency arguments, category mistake

INTRODUCTION

Abortion is one of the moral issues that has generated endless debates in the field of ethics. Controversies between the opponents and proponents of abortion abound concerning its different aspects. Among such controversies, currently ongoing, are abortion inconsistency arguments that some critics level

against the opponents of abortion. The critics, who are largely prochoice, argue that the opponents of abortion (the prolife) are inconsistent by opposing abortion while being silent about other ill conditions of life, like the cases of foetuses dying through miscarriage and the freezing and destruction of surplus IVF embryos. Hence, inconsistency arguments are criticisms against the opponents of abortion who claim that they do not care about life in other dangerous situations as they do in the case of abortion. Some prolife scholars have offered counterarguments against the inconsistency arguments. Prominent among them are Nicholas Colgrove, Bruce Philip Blackshaw and Daniel Rodger. Among their objections is that there is a huge diversity among the opponents of abortion, which inconsistent arguments ignore. Thus, they assert that inconsistency arguments are not tenable and do not matter.¹

Simkulet, a philosopher at Cleveland State University, USA, is a proponent of inconsistency arguments. Like others, he argues that either the opponents of abortion do more to prevent miscarriage and other cases involving threats to life or they should refrain from opposing abortion. He rejects the defence of the opponents of abortion against the inconsistency arguments, and insists that inconsistency arguments still matter and are morally significant.² He emphasizes the failure of opponents of abortion to prevent miscarriage and sees it as constituting an inconsistency in their belief and action systems.

To advance the prolife defence, this paper is a critique of Simkulet's inconsistency arguments. Acknowledging the response of some opponents of abortion that justifies their prioritisation of opposing abortion over preventing miscarriage on the ground that while abortion is preventable miscarriage is largely unpreventable, and underscoring the fact that while abortion is a deliberate act, miscarriage is not, the paper argues that Simkulet falls into category mistake in his treatment of miscarriage as if it belongs to the same category with abortion. The paper is divided into six sections. The first section is for conceptual clarifications; the second presents the arguments of the opponents of abortion; the third, the inconsistency arguments; the fourth, the prolife defence; the fifth, Simkulet's criticism of the prolife defence; and finally,

¹N. Colgrove, B. P. Blackshaw, & D. Rodger, 'Prolife Hypocrisy: Why Inconsistency Arguments Do not Matter,' *Journal of Medical Ethics*, (2020), 1, <<https://doi.org/10.1136/medethics-2020-106633>> accessed 15 January 2025

²W. Simkulet, 'The Moral Significance of Abortion Inconsistency Arguments,' *Asian Bioethics Review*, 14 (2022), <<https://doi.org/10.1007/s41649-021-00189-9>> accessed 5 February 2025

the sixth section presents criticisms of Simkulet as having fallen into a category mistake in his inconsistency argument against the prolife.

1. CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATIONS

1.1 *Abortion*

Abortion is a wilful termination of human pregnancy, often done in the early weeks of the pregnancy. However, some scholars apply the term not only to the deliberate pregnancy termination but also to the inadvertent and accidental loss of pregnancy, otherwise known as miscarriage. They consider all cases of loss of pregnancy as abortion, establishing two types of it, namely, spontaneous and induced abortions. The former refers to miscarriages, while the latter refers to abortions procured through human agency.³ Be that as it may, in this paper, the terms 'abortion' and 'induced abortion' are used interchangeably to refer to deliberate termination of pregnancy, while miscarriage and spontaneous abortion are used interchangeably to refer to the inadvertent and accidental loss of pregnancy.

1.2 *Inconsistency Arguments*

The inconsistency arguments are views that challenge the position of the prolife and anti-abortionists on what their critics perceive as contradictory or hypocrisy in their beliefs and actions, which undermines their opposition to abortion. The critics argue that the opponents of abortion manifest inconsistency in their moral beliefs by fundamentally claiming the status of personhood for fetuses from conception, whereas they neglect to promote the welfare of fetuses spontaneously aborted by natural causes (the cases of miscarriage) and fail to care about the well-being of the excess frozen human embryos usually created for *In Vitro* Fertilisation (IVF). In other words, "Proponents of inconsistency arguments argue that opponents of abortion hold inconsistent moral beliefs, arguing that upon revision, they will conclude that they either (i) need to do more, or (ii) need not oppose abortion."⁴

1.3 *Category Mistake*

Category mistake is the problem of placing a concept in a class of concepts it does not belong to, and making a judgment about the class without proper distinction. It makes judgments that would be correct about concepts rightly belonging to the class erroneous about the concept mistakenly placed

³Deepika & P. Kumar, 'Abortion and miscarriage: an understanding,' *The International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 9/1 (2021), <DOI: 10.25215/0901.046> accessed 7 March 2025

⁴Simkulet, 'The Moral Significance,' 42

there. When a mango is placed in a class of birds and perceived as an animal, it is a category mistake. Gilbert Ryle employed the yardstick of category mistake in his argument against Rene Descartes' mind-body dualism whereby he demonstrates that Cartesian dualism arises from Descartes' treatment of the concept of mind as something belonging to the categories of physical sciences: "a person's thinking, feeling and purposive doing cannot be described solely in the idioms of physics, chemistry and physiology, therefore they must be described in counterpart idioms."⁵

Ryle illustrates category mistake with a story of a foreigner to Oxford or Cambridge who visits it for the first time and is shown several colleges, libraries, scientific departments, museums, playing fields, and administrative offices of the University. At the end of the tour round the University, he asks, "But where is the University? I have seen where the members of the Colleges live, where the Registrar works, where the scientists experiment and the rest. But I have not yet seen the University in which reside and work the members of your University."⁶ Ryle considers it a category mistake that the visitor thinks of the University as if it were part of the category of buildings, whereas the University is the collection and unity of operation of the various structures which the visitor has seen. The concept of the University does not belong to the category of the parts of the University. A judgment made about a concept placed in a category that it does not belong to as if it belongs to the category, amounts to a judgmental error.

2. PROLIFE ARGUMENTS AGAINST ABORTION

Most anti-abortion arguments are grounded on the belief that human foetuses are persons from the moment of conception and are referred to as personhood-at-conception (PAC) argument. Judith Jarvis Thomson summarises them in two phases of syllogism. While in the first phase, the right to life of the foetus is established; in the second, the impermissibility of abortion is deduced from the foetus's right to life.

Phase 1

- The foetus is a person from the moment of conception.
- Every person has a right to life.

⁵G. Ryle, *The Concept of Mind*, (London: Routledge, 2009), 8.

⁶Ryle, *The Concept of Mind*, 6

- Therefore, the foetus has a right to life.⁷

Phase 2

- The mother has a right to decide what shall happen in and to her body.
- But surely a person's right to life is stronger and more stringent than the mother's right to decide what happens in and to her body, and so outweighs it.
- Therefore, the foetus may not be killed; an abortion may not be performed.⁸

There are diverse views which PAC theorists hold as reasons for the moral status of foetuses; Some, like Don Marquis, hold that foetuses matter based on the fact that they are biologically humans and have a future of value.⁹ For Jack Mulder, foetuses matter because they are human organisms;¹⁰ and for Patrick Lee and Robert P. George, they matter because they are of rational substance.¹¹ Even though the PAC theorists have a common belief that personhood begins at the moment of conception, they justify the belief on different grounds.

3. INCONSISTENCY ARGUMENTS AGAINST THE PROLIFE

Colgrove, Blackshaw and Rodger articulate various issues which theorists of the inconsistency arguments generally raised against the opponents of abortion: firstly, the opponents of abortion do keep silent or show no concern about the cases of spontaneous abortion (miscarriages); secondly, they refuse to adopt unwanted children; and, thirdly, they refuse to adopt and implant IVF surplus embryos lying in laboratories.¹² Furthermore, some critics tag opponents of abortion pejoratively as 'pro-birth' instead of 'prolife,' on the alleged ground that they only oppose abortion while not caring about the healthcare and social

⁷J. J. Thomson, 'A Defence of Abortion,' *Philosophy and Public Affairs*, 1/1 (1971), no. 3, <<https://learning.hccs.edu/faculty/james.ireland/phil1301/supplemental-readings/judith-jarvis-thomson-a-defense-of-abortion/view>> accessed 15 March 2025

⁸Thomson, 'A Defence of Abortion,' no. 3

⁹D. Marquis, 'Why Abortion is Immoral,' *Journal of Philosophy*, 86/4 (1989), <<https://doi.org/10.2307/2026961>> accessed 30 January 2025

¹⁰J. Mulder, 'A Short Argument Against Abortion Rights,' *Think*, 12/34 (2013), <<https://doi.org/10.1017/S1477175613000080>> accessed 28 January 2025

¹¹P. Lee, & R. P. George, 'The Wrong of Abortion,' in Cohen, A. I. & Wellman, C. H. (eds). *Contemporary Debates in Applied Ethics*, (2005), 13-26.

<<http://www.blackwellpublishing.com...PDFTheWrongofAbortion-BlackwellPublishing>> accessed 11 February 2025

¹²Colgrove *et al*, 'Prolife Hypocrisy,' 1

support system of children already born. Hence, they claim that opponents of abortion are “inconsistent hypocrites who either do not believe what they profess or fail to live accordingly.”¹³

What follows are some instances of such critics of opponents of abortion, according to Colgrove *et al* and Simkulet:¹⁴

- Bovens criticises the opponents of abortions as inconsistent for opposing contraceptives which have abortifacient tendencies in birth control, whereas they endorse the rhythm method for natural family planning (which he claims has the potential to cause more embryonic death overall).
- Harris criticises the opponents of abortion for permitting natural reproduction but prohibiting embryo creation for research purposes, since both processes require the sacrifice of embryos in achieving some other targeted and expected beneficial objectives.
- Stretton renders the view that if opponents of abortion believed abortion to be murder, it would seem justifiable for them to kill an abortion doctor who is about to perform the act of abortion.
- Chittister, who chastises those who regard themselves as prolife for their neglect of the welfare of persons already born.
- Simkulet accuses opponents of abortion of hypocrisy for not adopting and raising orphans, as they are compelling others to do what they do not want to do in the cases of bearing unwanted pregnancy instead of abortion.

Furthermore, Simkulet makes a distinction between moralism and restrictivism as two different groups of opponents of abortion. While the latter holds that social policies should be adopted to restrict access of pregnant women to induced abortion, moralists are of the view that abortion is merely immoral and does not make any demand for the adoption of social policies to restrict its procurement. Simkulet contends that opponents of abortion are restrictivists and that it is easy to see it from their PAC theoretical perspective: “foetuses are comparable to adult human persons, and society has adopted policies aimed at protecting the rights

¹³Colgrove *et al.*, ‘Prolife Hypocrisy,’ 1

¹⁴Colgrove *et al.*, ‘Prolife Hypocrisy,’ 1 & Simkulet, ‘The Moral Significance,’ 42

of adult human persons, so it is *prima facie* plausible that we should adopt similar social policies regarding fetuses.”¹⁵

Simkulet asserts that recent critics have argued that if the PAC theory were to be adopted, which revolves around the claim for the moral status of fetuses as persons having the right to life, the opponents of abortion should have much more to do than merely opposing induced abortion. Their restrictivist position should extend to all cases where human life is at stake. According to Simkulet,

Upwards of 60% of all human fetuses are spontaneously aborted. If fetuses matter, then we ought to oppose spontaneous abortion. Each year, many born persons suffer and die from a lack of access to food, shelter and medical care. If personhood matters, then we ought to do more. Critics argue that PAC theorists act inconsistently when they focus on preventing the problem of induced abortion, but leave scourges like spontaneous abortion, surplus frozen embryos from in vitro fertilisation (IVF), risky methods of contraception, capital punishment and poverty largely unaddressed¹⁶

The inconsistency theorists have a trend of firstly specifying what they think the opponents of abortion should believe or the action they should embark on to be consistent. Secondly, they go on to argue that the opponents of abortion are typically not doing those things. Then, thirdly, they conclude that either the opponents of abortion should stop opposing abortion or they should adjust their beliefs and actions in such a way as to meet what consistency demands.¹⁷ In this trend, Simkulet claims that the opponents of abortion ought to be preventing miscarriage. He goes on to stress that they fail to do so. Then, he finally concludes that they face the dilemma: “either they (i) need to do more to prevent foetal death, or (ii) should withdraw opposition to induced abortion.”¹⁸

4. PROLIFE DEFENCE

Colgrove, Blackshaw and Rodger champion the defence against the inconsistency arguments in their series of works. They present three major points

¹⁵Simkulet, ‘The Moral Significance,’ 44

¹⁶Simkulet, ‘The Inconsistency Argument,’ 1.

¹⁷Colgrove *et al.*, ‘Prolife Hypocrisy,’ 1

¹⁸Simkulet, ‘The Moral Significance,’ 42

of objections to the inconsistency arguments, namely, the Diversity Objection, Other Beliefs Objection and Other Actions Objection. The Diversity Objection addresses and rejects the inconsistency arguments on the ground that they lack consideration of the wide variety that characterises opponents of abortion. They are too specific in what they expect from the opponents of abortion and seem to ignore the fact that wide range of different religious and political communities make up the group of anti-abortionists. “Insofar as [inconsistency] arguments make sweeping claims about their habits, priorities, beliefs, values, and/or actions, such arguments commonly rely on unjustified overgeneralisations (or stereotypes).”¹⁹

Second, the Other Beliefs Objection contends that it is imperative to examine the other beliefs of the opponents of abortion before concluding what they should do. For instance, an opponent of abortion who believes that to kill is morally far worse than to let die may have priority of preventing killings incurred through induced abortion over preventing miscarriages.²⁰ Blackshaw, Colgrove and Rodger justify the priority of opposing induced abortion over preventing spontaneous abortion as follows:

There is an obvious belief that justifies PAC theorists’ actions and priorities—PAC theorists believe that induced abortion is a more important priority than these other issues. This is not an unfounded belief. ...induced abortion is the leading preventable cause of death of human beings, as spontaneous abortions are largely unpreventable.²¹

Finally, the Other Actions Objection is of the view that many different options of action flow from one’s beliefs. Rather than being obliged to engage in only one particular action among multiple options, an opponent of abortion may reasonably embark on any option or combination of several options depending on the available resources. For instance, the belief that every embryo is morally valuable can make someone choose either to oppose abortion or to focus on protecting frozen embryo in IVF laboratory. As many opponents of abortion do,

¹⁹B. P. Blackshaw, N. Colgrove & D. Rodger, ‘Why Inconsistency Arguments Fail: A Response to Shaw,’ *The New Bioethics*, (2022)1-13, 2, <DOI:10.1080/20502877.2022.2070960> accessed 15 February 2025

²⁰Blackshaw *et al.*, ‘Why Inconsistency Arguments Fail,’ 2

²¹B. P. Blackshaw, N. Colgrove, D. Rodger, ‘Inconsistency Arguments still Do not Matter,’ *Journal of Medical Ethics*, 2021, <<https://doi.org/10.1136/medet-hics-2021-107644>.> accessed 16 February 2025

if one believes that embryos have equal value with more developed human beings, one may choose to dedicate his time and resources to protecting more developed human beings.²²

Upon making their arguments, Colgrove, Blackshaw and Rodger assert that even if inconsistency arguments were to be successful, they do not matter, for they merely reveal the hypocrisy of some opponents of abortion. Inconsistency arguments, at best, demonstrate that some opponents of abortion do not live up to the demands of their beliefs, but not that there is a contradiction in their beliefs. “Most inconsistency arguments, if they do succeed, demonstrate hypocrisy on the part of OAs [that is, opponents of abortion], not inconsistent beliefs. While this is a serious charge that deserves thoughtful responses, it does not entail that OAs’ beliefs are contradictory and must be revised.”²³

5. WILLIAM SIMKULET’S REJECTION OF PROLIFE DEFENCE

In his response to the prolife’s Other Beliefs Objection, Simkulet criticises the prolife’s prioritisation of opposition to abortion over miscarriage, which is based on their claim that while spontaneous abortion is unpreventable, induced abortion is preventable. He contends that spontaneous abortion ought not to be seen as unpreventable and refers to Amy Berg’s argument that challenges such beliefs with reference to the progress made in the treatment of AIDS and other diseases. Berg argues that:

If we owe fetuses less moral concern, we may not have to try to overcome the medical obstacles to preventing miscarriage. But imagine throwing up our hands about a horrible disease that kills 22–89 % of born persons. Imagine saying that we should let AIDS, or cancer, or heart disease take its course, rather than expending more effort researching how we might prevent that disease or treat people who contract it. That’s not what we do. ... In just a couple of decades, AIDS went from a mysterious underground disease to a devastating and fatal epidemic to a relatively manageable chronic condition.²⁴

²²Blackshaw *et al.*, ‘Why Inconsistency Arguments Fail,’ 2

²³Colgrove *et al.*, ‘Prolife Hypocrisy,’ 5

²⁴A. Berg, ‘Abortion and Miscarriage,’ *Philosophical Studies*, 174/5 (2017), 1221, <<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11098-016-0750-z>> accessed 17 January 2025

Simkulet goes on to reject the Other Actions Objection as well, insisting that some other actions which the opponents of abortion embark on are not enough. The opponents of abortion have defended their position against the inconsistency theory that, moved by the belief that foetuses matter, some of them can justifiably embark on lobbying to change the laws of IVF to reduce the number of embryos produced in the IVF process or any other actions required in the preservation of life, affordable within one's resources. Simkulet maintains that such action is not enough. He advocates that the opponents of abortion should see it as obligatory to gestate and adopt the surplus IVF embryos, if the embryos really matter as they claim with their PAC theory. He further argues that Other Beliefs Objection and Other Actions Objection, if they were to be true, then the result would be the end of ethics, for it would make moral analysis impossible. He writes:

No person has merely one moral belief, so if a diversity of beliefs invalidates moral analysis, ethics is impossible. In all cases in which a person acts morally responsibly ... agents have other possible actions, so if merely having other actions was sufficient to disregard moral analysis, ethics fails.²⁵

6. CRITIQUE OF SIMKULET

As stated above, Simkulet argues that based on their inconsistency, the opponents of abortion are faced with the dilemma of either doing more to prevent miscarriage or withdrawing their opposition to induced abortion. On the contrary, this dilemma is grounded on a category mistake Simkulet makes by speaking about spontaneous abortion (miscarriage) as if it entirely belongs to the same category as induced abortion on moral analysis.

An induced abortion is a deliberate termination of pregnancy through human agency, whereas spontaneous abortion is not a deliberate act and is not carried out directly by human agency. While moral responsibility of a human agent is directly involved in the act of induced abortion, there is no moral responsibility of a human agent directly carrying out a miscarriage. While induced abortion belongs to the category of acts that essentially involve moral responsibility of a human agency, spontaneous abortion does not. No one can be held as directly morally responsible for a particular act of spontaneous abortion, but all those deliberately involved in performing and sponsoring an act of

²⁵Simkulet, 'The Moral Significance,' 49

induced abortion are morally responsible for it. In a word, while induced abortion is a human act, miscarriage is not. Hence, it is a category mistake to treat spontaneous abortion and induced abortion as if both belong entirely to the same class of human acts. Thus, the choice of dedicating one's resources to opposing induced abortion and not equally preventing spontaneous abortion does not amount to inconsistency; neither does it entail a moral obligation for the anti-abortionists to either equally dedicate their resources to preventing spontaneous abortion or to stop opposing induced abortion.

Moreover, it is important to note that the fundamental belief system that informs opponents of abortion is not only their belief in the status of foetuses as human persons and their right to life, but also the belief that no human being has the right to terminate the life of an innocent person. This seems to be forgotten or intentionally ignored by Simkulet and some other inconsistent theorists. In the case of miscarriage, the belief that no human being has the right to terminate the life of an innocent person is not affected, whereas it is trampled upon in the case of induced abortion. Hence, the opponents of abortion are not inconsistent in their beliefs and actions when they choose to have greater concern in battling against induced abortion than spontaneous abortion. Such a preference does not constitute any dilemma, since the fundamentals of their belief system, which motivate them into opposition to induced abortion, are not equally affected in the same way in the case of miscarriage. It would then be ridiculous to expect opponents of abortion to approach the problem of miscarriage with the same belief system with which they oppose induced abortion.

Our criticisms of Simkulet's inconsistency arguments do not imply that opponents of abortion do not have any moral obligation towards the prevention of miscarriage. While it is a category mistake to do a moral analysis of miscarriage as if it is entirely of the same category as induced abortion, the category mistake can be avoided by doing the moral analysis of miscarriage on a different ground, which would make manifest the proper nature of the moral obligation to prevent miscarriage. The moral analysis would, of course, not involve the belief that no one has the right to terminate the life of an innocent life, since there is no human agency in spontaneous abortion, but would involve the belief in the personhood of the foetuses and their right to life. A third important belief that should be identified in the moral analysis of miscarriage is the couple's right to proper health care. This is because the case of miscarriage has a lot to do with the health condition of the couples and largely requires

medical remedies.²⁶ In this way, the obligation to prevent miscarriage cannot be exactly of the same category in all aspects as the obligation to prevent abortion. A belief system that obliges one to work towards prevention of miscarriage may not necessarily imply a contradiction if it does not oblige one to dedicate equal time and resources towards preventing abortion. Likewise, as already argued above, the belief system of the opponents of abortion may not necessarily imply any contradiction when they do not devote the same attention to preventing miscarriage.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we have seen that Simkulet, like other abortion inconsistency theorists, argues that opponents of abortion are inconsistent for not acting to prevent miscarriage as they oppose induced abortion. He holds that the motivating factor of opponents of abortion is their belief that fetuses are persons and have the right to life. While we admit this as what informs the opponents of abortion, we have observed that Simkulet either forgets or undermines a third belief that no one has the right to terminate the life of an innocent person as part of the fundamental beliefs that inform the opposition to abortion. We have also argued that Simkulet treats induced abortion as if it belongs to the same category as miscarriage and thus falls into a category mistake. Hence, the inconsistency and the dilemma that Simkulet claims to exist in abortion opposition are groundless. If the prochoice are dedicating their resources to opposing abortion, they do not need to stop the opposition simply because they are not dedicating similar resources towards preventing miscarriage, for as we have seen, there is no contradiction in choosing to oppose abortion and not equally choosing to prevent miscarriage.

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²⁶I. A. Abdelazim, M. AbuFaza, P. Purohit, & R. H. Farag, 'Miscarriage Definitions, Causes and Management: Review of Literature,' *ARC Journal of Gynecology and Obstetrics*, 2/3, (2017), 20-31, <<http://dx.doi.org/10.20431/2456-0561.0203005>> accessed 15 January 2025